

Treatment	1977 crop season			1978 crop Season		
	Weed population (no./m ²)	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weed population (no./m ²)	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)
	40 DT	at harvest		40 DT	at harvest	
<i>Main plot</i>						
Continuous 10 cm submergence to grain filling	67.6	18.5	3.5	59.3	15.8	3.3
Saturation to maturity and 5 cm submergence to dough stage	88.5	21.8	3.1	62.8	16.6	3.3
Saturation to grain filling	114.6	29.1	2.6	87.9	22.8	3.0
<i>Subplot^a</i>						
Fluchloralin EC @ 0.8 kg a.i./ha	23.3	12.6	3.4	38.1	9.4	3.3
2,4-D EE (G) @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	30.8	14.2	3.3	40.5	11.2	3.3
Butachlor (G) @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	46.1	14.8	3.2	56.7	10.4	3.1
Thiobencarb (G) @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	52.8	15.9	3.1	39.5	9.2	3.3
Manual weeding at 25 and 50 days after planting	37.1	13.0	3.3	39.3	9.8	3.3
Unweeded control	233.7	70.4	2.5	156.8	58.4	2.7
CD (0.05) for water management practice	4.9	3.0	0.3	1.4	1.4	0.2
CD (0.05) for herbicides	8.4	2.7	0.5	4.3	1.3	0.3

^a Fluchloralin was applied as preplanting soil spray a day before transplanting; granular formulations of 2,4-D EE, butachlor, and thiobencarb were applied directly 7 days after transplanting (DT).

management.

Continuous submergence from 7 days

after planting to harvest recorded the highest grain yields. Preplanting treat-

ment with fluchloralin recorded the maximum grain yield. ■

Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Efficacy of brodifacoum baits against rodents in storage areas

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Brodifacoum is a new anticoagulant rodenticide of exceptional activity against rodent species both resistant and susceptible to other conventional rodenticides. The formulated product, which contains 50 ppm active ingredient (a.i.), is highly toxic and can provide a single-feeding action for many species. It compares with Warfarin baits containing 250 ppm a.i. in its adverse effect to man and domestic animals. Accidental poisoning can be countered with treatments of Vitamin K₁.

Baiting tests at the short-term storage room and seed processing lab of the International Rice Research Institute showed that brodifacoum pellet baits were effective in controlling mice infestations.

During the 26-day baiting period, high bait intake was followed by decline

1. Daily consumption of brodifacoum bait at the Rice Genetic Resources Laboratory storage room, IIRRI, 1980.

and death of mice (Fig. 1). That indicated migrants or even new-generation mice from births in the original population just before control.

A long-term baiting trial indicated that mice population was kept at satisfactorily low levels by maintaining adequate baiting points. Better control was

Consumption (%)

2. Bait consumption during a long-term baiting test at the IRRI Rice Genetic Resources Laboratory, 1981.

attained by baiting all possible breeding areas (Fig. 2).

Mice in the storage rooms fed on pelletized baits despite the abundance of

rice, showing the attractiveness of the bait. ■

Irrigation and water management

Water management in dry season rice

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Dry season rice in West Bengal requires large quantities (170-180 cm) of water, 50-60% of which is lost in deep percolation because of continuous deep submergence of fields. Water requirements can be reduced. The medium-duration (120 days) rice cultivar IET 2815 was grown on clay loam with 8 water management practices (see table). Yields were higher with 10-0 cm water from transplanting to yellow ripe stage than with 5-0 cm. Irrigating the crop 2 days after complete recession of 10-cm standing water did not reduce grain yield from that obtained by irrigating sooner, but the irrigation requirement was

Influence of 8 water management practices on grain yield and irrigation requirement of dry season rice in West Bengal.

Water management practice	Grain yield (t/ha)			Av irrigation requirement ^a (cm)
	1977-78	1978-79	Av	
10-0 cm water regime from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.8	5.0	4.4	180 (18)
5-0 cm water regime from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.6	4.1	3.8	100 (20)
Stress ^b during early tillering, no stress ^c during rest	3.4	4.3	3.8	90 (18)
Stress during late tillering, no stress during rest	3.7	4.3	4.0	90 (18)
Stress during flowering, no stress during rest	3.6	4.0	3.8	90 (18)
Stress during grain filling, no stress during rest	3.8	4.7	4.2	90 (18)
10 cm irrigation 2 days after recession of standing water, from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.9	5.1	4.5	140 (14)
5 cm irrigation 2 days after recession of standing water, from transplanting to yellow ripe stage	3.8	4.8	4.3	80 (16)
C.D. (5%)	0.24	0.15		

^aThe figures in parentheses denote number of irrigations. ^bStress: application of 5 cm water 2 days after recession to 0 cm. ^cNo stress: application of 5 cm water immediately after recession to 0 cm.

reduced by 20-22%. The flowering stage was found most sensitive and the grain-

filling stage least sensitive to water stress. ■